

Precision Photometric Exoplanet Observations with the WIYN 0.9m Telescope

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The WIYN 0.9m Telescope Half Degree Imager (HDI) has been used for two exciting programs that explore the properties of transiting exoplanets around nearby M-dwarf host stars. M-dwarfs form the vast majority of all stars in our galaxy, and they are therefore our most common neighbors. We now know that these stars commonly host planets. Understanding the architectures of these systems is a first step in the search for habitable planets.

One of the programs [1] found a surprisingly dense Neptune-sized planet in a short-period eccentric orbit around its host star in the Hyades cluster. The other result [2] revealed the orbital period of a newly discovered warm Jupiter from the *Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite* (TESS) mission, and the largest planet known to transit an M-dwarf star. Both programs used a new “Engineered Diffuser”—a nanofabricated optical device that is capable of molding the image of a star into a broad and stabilized top-hat shape—which has been installed and commissioned for use on the WIYN 0.9m Telescope for high-precision photometric work.

For the dense-Neptune program, Jayadev Rajagopal, Flynn Haase, and Lori Allen formed the NOIRLab team that collaborated with Principal Investigator Guðmundur Stefánsson (Princeton University) to install an Engineered Diffuser on HDI for precision photometric work on the WIYN 0.9m Telescope (Figure 1). The diffuser uses precision-engineered micro-lenselets to spread the light over many pixels in a stable manner that minimizes photometric errors due to seeing variations and averages over inter-pixel sensitivity effects. It thus enables observations of bright, nearby planet-hosting stars, including a number of recently discovered *TESS* planet candidates, with high observing efficiencies and photometric precision.

During commissioning observations for the Engineered Diffuser on the WIYN 0.9m Telescope, the team observed four transits of the young M-dwarf planet K2-25b to better constrain its orbital properties. K2-25b is a Neptune-sized planet in a 3.5-day orbit around its M4.5 dwarf host star in the ~ 600-Myr-old Hyades cluster. These observations

Figure 1. An example of a 5 cm x 5 cm (2 inch x 2 inch) Engineered Diffuser similar to the one installed on the WIYN 0.9m Telescope. It molds the image of a star into a broad and stabilized top-hat shape. (Credit: G. Stefánsson/RPC Photonics)

directly supplemented observations taken with other telescopes, including diffuser-assisted observations on the 3.5m Telescope at Apache Point Observatory (APO) and spectroscopic observations with the Habitable-zone Planet Finder (HPF) on the 10m Hobby-Eberly Telescope (HET) at McDonald Observatory. By combining the diffuser-assisted data and the radial velocity (RV) data, the team provided the first measurement of the mass and density of this planet, showing that K2-25b is surprisingly dense for its size and age, suggesting that K2-25b has a large core. K2-25b could either be composed of a rocky core (95% of the mass) enveloped by a 5% H/He atmosphere or even have a higher core mass fraction if it has a high fraction of water/ices in its core. More observations, such as transmission spectroscopic observations with the *James Webb Space Telescope (JWST)* in the future, are needed to distinguish between these composition scenarios.

To gain further insight into the formation and evolution history of the young K2-25b system, some of the diffuser-assisted observations from the WIYN 0.9m Telescope and the 3.5m Telescope at APO were conducted simultaneously with RV observations during transit with the HPF to conduct the first Rossiter-McLaughlin (RM) effect observations of the planet (Figure 2). The RM effect relies on measuring the RV anomaly that occurs as the planet transits its host star, successively blocking blue-and-red shifted light on the rotating stellar disk. The shape and amplitude of the RV anomaly are dependent on the obliquity of the system, the angle between the planet's orbit and the star's equator. The observations demonstrated that the planet's orbit is well aligned with the spin-axis of its host star, in contrast to a number of other hot Neptune-sized planets, which have been observed to orbit on highly misaligned and even polar orbits. This suggests that K2-25b likely formed and evolved via a different mechanism than the population of misaligned hot Neptunes. The result has been highlighted in a [NOIRLab press release](#).

For the second program, the WIYN team collaborated with Principal Investigator Caleb Cañas (Pennsylvania State University) to confirm the planetary nature of and characterize a warm Jupiter-sized planet, TOI-1899 b, recently discovered by *TESS*. *TESS* observed only a single transit during a timespan of ~50 days, which led the team to observe four nights of TOI-1899 with HDI in search of an additional transit. These photometric observations directly supplemented observations (see Figure 3) taken at other telescopes, including photometry from the 0.5m ARC Small Aperture Telescope at APO, high-contrast imaging from the WIYN 3.5m Telescope and the 3m Shane Telescope at Lick Observatory, and spectroscopic observations with HPF. Though the HDI observations did not catch a transit, they further demonstrate the complementary use of these multiple techniques.

With these data, the team confirmed that TOI-1899 b is a planet ten percent larger in radius than Jupiter and orbits a cool star with a period of 29 days. While hundreds of Jupiter-sized planets have been discovered orbiting larger Sun-like stars, it is rare to see these planets orbiting low-mass stars. TOI-1899 is only the fifth known M-dwarf to host a transiting Jupiter-sized planet and the first of such systems with an orbital period longer than four days. Despite the comparatively long orbital period, this still

places the giant planet much closer to its star than expected from classical formation theories. Future observations of the RM effect (similar to K2-25 b) for TOI-1899 b could help constrain if this warm Jupiter migrated to its current location or formed there.

The nature of the host star and the long orbital period also make TOI-1899 b a candidate for future atmospheric studies. The radius of TOI-1899 b is slightly larger than planetary models predict for cool, non-irradiated Jupiter-sized planets, which cannot be inflated by heating from the host star. With the wavelength coverage and precision of the upcoming *JWST*, it will be possible to observe features in the atmosphere of TOI-1899 and begin to constrain the exact source of this apparent inflation.

References

- [1] Stefansson, G., et al. 2020, *AJ*, 160, 192S
- [2] Cañas, C., et al. 2020, *AJ*, 160, 147C

Figure 2. *Top*: Example diffuser-assisted photometric observations taken with the Engineered Diffuser on the WIYN 0.9m Telescope of the transit of K2-25b. *Bottom*: In total, four transits were obtained with the WIYN 0.9m Telescope, one of which was taken simultaneously with in-transit RV observations with the HPF Spectrograph on the 10m HET. The data show that K2-25b's orbit is well aligned with the equator of its host star. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA)

Figure 3. *Left*: The single transit of TOI-1899 b observed by *TESS*. Precise characterization of the transiting planet requires additional data to determine the orbital period. *Right*: The top part displays the HPF RVs which were necessary to determine TOI-1899 b takes ~29 days to orbit its star. The vertical lines indicate nights where HDI photometric observations were obtained. The HDI photometry is displayed on the bottom row where no transits were observed. (From [2], with permission)